

Operational Avionics Smart Instrumentation System (OASIS)

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ABSTRACT

The prevailing data collection systems and approaches in use today are being overwhelmed by the amount of data generated by current generation avionics. Future avionics, using integrated processors and multi-spectral data fusion, will increase by a factor of 10-100 the amount of data available for analysis. Without techniques for automatically deciding what data is important and when to record that data, the analyst trying to solve problems will either be swamped in data or missing key items. The Operational Avionics Smart Instrumentation System (OASIS) project provides technology for facility data collection and analysis systems while exploring the technology needed to incorporate advanced data collection and software anomaly detection systems into operational aircraft.

OPERATIONAL INSTRUMENTATION

Up front, it is important to note that OASIS is for ground-based software support and test facility and for as it is designed, operational use; the development of future flight test instrumentation systems for the evaluation of weapons systems in development is left for the Common Airborne Instrumentation System (CAIS), a joint-service program. For the most part, OASIS collects only the essential data needed to solve a software anomaly from fielded weapon systems avionics and from software support facility's avionics hot benches and mock-ups. This is counter to most test philosophies where it is more desirable to collect all data and worry about reduction and processing of data later. Each philosophy has its place.

The Effected Process

The use of OASIS technology in operational aircraft or software support facilities can favorably effect the operational flight program (OFP) update process. The current process is restricted in that data from

operational missions lack the engineering data that would isolate a software anomaly (see Figure 1). This is unfortunate because as operational aircraft become more software intensive, the amount of data available to isolate a software anomaly increases. With no on-board assets to capture operational data (other than pilot write-ups and display videos), there are missed opportunities to obtain the hard engineering data in the mission environment that could result in rapid turnaround of a software fix to an operational software anomaly.

Figure 1: No Engineering Data From Field

The Need

The OASIS phased development allows for gradual implementation of the advanced data collection and analysis technologies - first, in the ground-based software test and support facilities - then, eventually, and hopefully, migrating into the weapon system platform. The need for OASIS type technologies is well documented in various DOD publications. The Air Force has conducted various studies to determine how to best improve operational software support and readiness for it's weapons systems. In most studies, various types of operational instrumentation and/or data collection systems have been noted as a driving requirement to technologically prepare for a better process and near real-time realization of software

anomaly detection, capture, isolation, analysis and solution turn-around. [1,2,3,6,12]

Background Studies

In the area of software turnaround for radar system two leading studies, the Radar Readiness Technology studies conducted independently by Hughes Aircraft Company and TRW (both concluding in 1989) under contract to the Air Force, made it abundantly clear that without software anomaly data capture, there will not be a significant improvement in rapid turnaround and software readiness in these sophisticated components of modern aircraft weapons systems [1,2]. These studies have provided the baseline for the OASIS system.

Initial Conception

The OASIS building-block approach was conceived in 1990 as the result of a meeting of weapons systems software managers and engineers attending the Test Facility Working Group (TFWG)[3]. The Air Force was already pursuing development of the HADIS system and was considering a full development of the entire OASIS concept in one project. The problem was cost and the various technological hurdles that needed to be overcome for OASIS to work. In addition, many of the TFWG members were uncertain that technology for OASIS could be sold in its entirety to the field when the project ended. At the same time, it was noted that the various necessary technology hurdles and milestones along the way to a full OASIS concept could actually produce smaller technology achievements that could be used sooner by the field and the various TFWG member weapons system software facilities. Hence, the various OASIS phased efforts were born.

OASIS PHASES

The OASIS effort includes the recently completed High-speed Avionics Data Instrumentation System (HADIS), the in-flight capable Data Integration and Collection Environment (DICE), the Multi-source Smart Interface Controller (MUSIC) and the Generic Adaptive Mission Event System (GAMES). HADIS enables collection and basic analysis of very high speed data from radar and electronic warfare systems including in-phase and quadrature (I&Q) data. DICE is a reprogrammable data collection flight-worthy prototype with system specific event-driven activation logic. MUSIC non-intrusively taps into multiple avionics data sources and provides innovative event capturing and data flagging features. By intelligently collecting data from avionics systems, the MUSIC eliminates the need to tailor the data collection

parameters for every test or mission. GAMES incorporates artificial intelligence and automatic processing features to produce a novel data collection and analysis environment for avionics of the future. Depending on the characteristics of the Operational Flight Program, OASIS GAMES could provide temporary amelioration of an operational software anomaly allowing for mission completion and then rapid turnaround of emergency software changes.

The resultant system of OASIS advances the state-of-the-art in mission and ground-based facility data collection and analysis for supplying needed information to field users and maintainers of avionics, ultimately creating a capability for rapid reprogramming and improving the software readiness posture of weapon systems. This paper discusses the building-block research and development approach and technologies of OASIS.

PHASE 1: HIGH-SPEED AVIONICS DATA INSTRUMENTATION SYSTEM (HADIS)

The Air Force has a continuing need to access digital signal processing data to provide a more detailed understanding of radar systems and to provide organic capabilities to maintain these sophisticated systems. Most of this high-speed data is available on the radar system data buses in the signal processor and radar computer. Access to the information requires instrumenting these buses and passing the data to an external processing and recording system. Currently, the capability to access and analyze this detailed information exists in a few special laboratories operated primarily by radar manufacturers. The objective of the High-Speed Avionics Data Instrumentation System effort, completed in 1993, was to develop government owned methods and systems capable of facilitating the software update process of embedded avionics radar systems in digital format. This was to be accomplished by developing a generic instrumentation system for high-speed avionics data. This instrumentation system enables rapid anomaly identification and diagnosis in a test facility and provides a foundation for enhanced operational flight program testing for any avionics system that provides data to an external port. [4,5]

VME-Based Architecture

The HADIS backplane is VME-based. It utilizes both the VME bus and the VSB bus to give the system a throughput of 40 MByte/sec. The VME bus passes the control and command for the HADIS. While the VSB bus is dedicated data bus. The HADIS has a

capability of recording up to 13 MBytes/sec and can store a total of 40 GBytes of data on one AMPEX DCRSi tape. The 13 MBytes/sec is a limitation due to the AMPEX DCRSi recorder. At the time of the HADIS development the AMPEX DCRSi recorder was the state of the art recorder storage. [4,5]

Flexible Interfaces

The interfaces that were developed for the HADIS are what gives the HADIS its flexibility to extract data from any avionics system. The Xilinx logic cell arrays gives HADIS the capability to be configured without a hardware change. The change is internal to the Xilinx chips on the interface boards by downloading the software change to these chips. There are two interface boards required for each systems data bus. There are 4 Avionics Data I/O Boards and 4 Radar Data I/O Boards for a total of 8 developed I/O interface boards. The interface board technology is what future instrumentation technology will build upon. The HADIS technology is in use in various Air Force organizations and is the baseline for those OASIS efforts aimed at operational data collection. [4,5]

**PHASE 2:
DATA INTEGRATION AND COLLECTION
ENVIRONMENT (DICE)**

The need for a low cost instrumentation system that can be hosted on-board tactical aircraft to collect and record avionics data has resulted in the development of the Data Integration and Collection Environment (DICE) System currently in development by TRW Inc. under contract to Wright Laboratory, Wright-Patterson AFB OH.

The F-15 APG-63 Fire Control radar system was chosen as the testbed for the prototype (see Figure 2). This system was selected because of its relative complexity and tactical presence in today's air combat arena.

User Requirements

The desire to provide an open architecture system which is affordable, expandable, adaptable, reconfigurable and maintainable led to the formulation of the basic goals and requirements for a data collection system for tactical aircraft [7]. The basic requirements for this system are:

- Low cost (production & life-cycle support)
- Light weight
- Non-intrusive data collection

- High data storage capacity in digital format
- Maximized use of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS)
- Adaptable to multiple platforms
- Fit into available aircraft space with minimal modifications
- Minimal logistic support for the system.

The question of cost effective logistical support of the system is a prime concern for the prototyping effort. Towards this end, the DICE design makes every effort to use practical commercial technology. This ensures that as commercial technology improves, the military's technology keeps pace in a very cost effective manner.

Figure 2: F-15 Platform For DICE

Design Based On Commercial Technology

The prototype DICE system uses the Comtek Instrumentation Interface Unit as a source of it's data. This approach, a two-card set added to the APG-63 avionics suite, provides an interface for collecting sufficient radar data to assist an analyst in finding and resolving anomalies at the digital level. A similar methodology can be employed for other systems thus providing a quasi-standard interface (see Figure 3)[7,12].

The DICE system uses state-of-the-art field reprogrammable technology to define the communication interfaces for serial and parallel data. This feature is the key to the logistics support question. The ability to modify the hardware interface configuration through software means that the DICE system can be used to instrument different systems with the same hardware and be configured via software. Additionally, this feature allows the target

system to grow without requiring a new instrumentation set [6,7,12].

Figure 3: DICE Interfaces To Weapon System

For processing power, the current DICE system uses a 68030 processor in a VME backplane. This configuration allows substantial flexibility for peripheral and processor growth and expansion. The use of a commercial standard for the processor architecture provides a stable base for keeping abreast of the direction industry takes, therefore keeping the military's technology edge sharp. [7]

DICE system collects MIL-STD-1553B bus communications data using a commercial bus monitor which is VME compatible. The DICE system also uses a built-in time word generator synchronized to the aircraft mission time for time-tagging the collected data (see Figure 4). [7]

Figure 4: DICE Schematic

The DICE system uses a commercial 8 millimeter cartridge magnetic tape drive for data storage. This allows for compact data storage via a commercial standard system. This system can store 5 Giga Byte (166 minutes) worth of filtered data at 500 Kilo Byte sustained data rate. The system uses Small Computer Serial Interface, an industry standard, for data transmission to the recorder providing flexibility to host other recording media. To augment the

storage of data, the DICE system has software to intelligently filter data based on preselected criteria. This real-time software, written in Ada, allows an analyst to define what events determine the criteria for collecting data. This reduces the amount of non-essential data recorded and aids the analysts by recording only data of interest. [7,12]

DICE data can be played back to an analysis system which is configured to receive the actual avionics bus data, or the data tape could be used to play back to another analysis tool or simulator. For the F-15/APG-63, the analysis tool of choice which DICE data is compatible, is the Integrated Data Reduction and Analysis System (see Figure 3). [12]

PHASE 3: MULTI-SOURCE SMART INTERFACE CONTROLLER (MUSIC)

The MUSIC system is being designed to selectively instrument operational data to solve the avionics software anomalies in embedded computer systems (ECS). In order to obtain the characteristics of these anomalies in a timely manner, two software monitors within MUSIC system are designed to detect these anomaly events and collect only relevant avionics sensor data. A resource monitor (RM) is responsible for buffering and acquiring these avionics data using RM Avionics Data Interfaces (RMADI). A Degradation Monitor (DM) is responsible for detecting these anomaly events of avionics systems being instrumented using one of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques. [8,10]

Smart Features

The smart portion of MUSIC is its key ability to monitor sensor performance of an avionics system and to determine when anomalous behavior occurs. Anomalous behavior is any type of system operation which does not match with some theoretical ideal performances. This definition of anomalous behavior (AB) is deliberately broad and it is not expected that any realizable MUSIC system could actually fully perform this function. The primary class of anomalous behavior, which MUSIC system is expected to detect, is caused by events external to the instrumented system. In particular, MUSIC's primary function is to find those types of problems that usually appear during actual employment of the weapons system avionics; circumstances where it is very difficult to collect sufficient data to engineer a solution. The prototype MUSIC system will be eventually integrated and installed into the ground-based Mobile ECS Readiness Research Facility (MERRF). However, the MUSIC concepts

could be incorporated into the DICE system to perform the on-board smart instrumentation task while the operational aircraft can conduct its normal mission. The figure 1 shows a block diagram for the prototype MUSIC system which consisted of RM, DM, and recorder. [8,10]

Resource Monitor (RM)

The RM section contains the avionics data interfaces and manages the flow of data through the MUSIC system. The RM is also responsible for managing data buffering, acquisition, and recording resources. The RM consists of two sections: RM Data Manager (RMDM) and RM Avionics Data Interface (RMADI). The RMDM provides overall RM data routing, executive, and status functions. The RMADI provides the ability to interface with a wide variety of avionics data. The prototype MUSIC system is based on the HADIS technology and will provide APG-68 radar interfaces such as APinst bus, Digibus, PSP bus, and MIL-STD-1553. A high-speed interface board (HSIB) provides actual avionics bus interfaces and a high-speed data board actually provides data buffer and VME bus interfaces. These data must be managed on a source by source basis to allow selective recording of data based on detected anomalies. Each data source will be buffered to provide the ability to capture the data leading up to the anomalous event. [8,10,11]

Degradation Monitor (DM)

The DM is responsible for identifying anomalous behavior of the avionics systems being instrumented. The DM consists of two sections: DM Data Manager (DMDM) and DM Decision Analyzer (DMDA). The DMDM interfaces with the RM to acquire and format data for use by the DMDA. Typically, the DMDM will select certain subsets of data which the RM is acquiring. This data will then be formatted to allow easy access by the DMDA. This concept is employed to isolate the DMDA from the physical data interfaces since the DMDA may be some type of AI system. The MUSIC architecture allows more than one DMDA, each employing different approaches to the problems of anomaly detection. Candidate approaches are rule-based, neural nets, or fuzzy logic system. However, the prototype DMDA will use a rule-based approach combined with State Based Feature Recognition algorithm to detect the presence of events and trends in the avionics data to detect AB's. The MUSIC architecture easily allows to implement these algorithms so that the results of different DMDA could be formed for the fused solution, if necessary. By its very nature, the DMDA may actually consist of

several different hardware subsystems for implementing neural nets. [8,10,11]

Post Mission Mode

Another feature of MUSIC is borne from the MUSIC systems ability to operate in a post-mission mode that essentially allows a preliminary data filtering for visual analysis. The prototype also provides a framework for evaluating additional AI techniques such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Fuzzy Logic. Therefore, MUSIC will provide a testbed for detecting anomalous behaviors of SUT using various AI techniques. [8,10]

PHASE 4: GENERIC ADAPTIVE MISSION EVENT SYSTEM (GAMES)

A future step in the OASIS concept is the Generic Adaptive Mission Event System (GAMES). This phase will place enhanced artificial intelligence and automatic processing features into future systems. GAMES takes instrumentation systems an order of magnitude further by incorporating vast artificial intelligence, automatic processing and avionics interactive features into instrumentation systems of the future. Unlike existing instrumentation systems, including the previously mentioned HADIS, DICE and MUSIC efforts, all of which act passively, GAMES would act either passively (MUSIC component) or in it's most capable mode, interactively. GAMES like other OASIS technologies could be used in a software test/support facility or could be flown operationally. [1,9]

Electronic Analyst In The Air

In the operational scenario, GAMES interactive features would only operate under pilot command. Essentially, GAMES would have the capability of activating the various functions of avionics subsystems in order to collect interactive data from the operational environment. In addition, GAMES would have sufficient interactive capability with the avionics that the pilot could allow the avionics to operate in a GAMES test mode. In effect, GAMES provides an enhanced mission operation capability in the face of an unknown threat. In any event, GAMES technology would radically speed up the process of finding and correcting anomalies. [1,9]

THE TOTAL SYSTEM

Each phase of OASIS can be used independently for meeting a variety of needs or can be used together to form the baseline smart data collection and

intermediate analysis system in an operational or a ground-based environment. The combined OASIS system used in an operational environment would be a favorable benefit to the software OFP update process and conceivably would shave hours, days and even months off of the traditional process - data, much of it triggered from anomaly detection, from all points in process would be available (see Figure 5). The side benefits of a deployed system could be many from operational mission re-creation to real-time intelligence. Although it is the considered opinion that OASIS like technologies should be used operationally, a firm recommendation is deferred until data from the field is obtained and scrutinized for conclusive proof. Fortunately, the OASIS building-block approach allows this to happen in a budget conscious climate.

Figure 5: Data From All Points In Process

User's Perspective on Operational Instrumentation

The OASIS has various components that can be put to use in the operational world. The operational users have indicated, especially in this budget restricted environment, that gradual implementation of OASIS technologies is the most suitable tactic for now. The DICE system will allow the operational users to obtain the baseline data needed for future decisions. This is a prudent course and leaves it rightfully up to the TFWG members and the weapon systems software maintainers to prove that OASIS technologies will benefit the operational aircraft today and in the future in terms of cost-effectiveness and capability. [6,12]

In The Meantime

Most of the OASIS phases do not technically hinge on operational user decisions as they have multi-purpose benefits that can be used in ground-based software support environments and other areas as well. Various uses have been identified for OASIS technologies; many more uses are untapped.

SUMMARY

The OASIS project is about the synergistic use of data from multiple sources to extract the greatest amount of information possible about the immediate avionics data environment. The data obtained through the OASIS effort will be used to counter software deficiencies. OASIS could easily have been just one project with a product at the end. However, the building-block nature of OASIS provides tools and systems that can be used in the field as OASIS is being developed rather than when waiting until OASIS is completed.

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